

Sensor Specifications and Simulation Parameters

Parameter	Physical Specification	Simulated Specification	Simulation Limitations
Hokuyo UST-10LX			
Range	0.06m to 10m	<min>0.06</min> <max>10.0</max>	Perfect ray reflection; no scattering on glass/reflective surfaces
Field of View	270 deg (135 deg)	<min_angle>-2.356</min_angle> <max_angle>2.356</max_angle>	Zero hardware communication latency; infinite data bandwidth
Update Rate	40 Hz	<update_rate>15</update_rate>	Perfectly consistent timing (no jitter); reduced frequency due to hardware limitations
Sample (Resolution)	1080 steps (0.25 deg)	<samples>1080</samples>	No drop-outs or missed returns from dark objects
ZED Stereo Camera			
Resolution	1920 X 1080	<width>1920</width> <height>1080</height>	Perfect lens geometry (no distortion); reduced frequency due to hardware limitations
Field of View	110 deg	<horizontal_fov>1.919</horizontal_fov>	Perfect automatic exposure and zero motion blur
Depth Resolution	1280 X 720	<width>1280</width> <height>720</height>	Perfect depth calculation; immune to textureless walls or poor lighting
Depth Range	0.2m to 20m	<near>0.2</near> <far>20.0</far>	Perfect depth calculation; immune to textureless walls or poor lighting.
Update Rate	30 Hz	<update_rate>15</update_rate>	Zero USB transmission latency; reduced frequency due to hardware limitations